

INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL APPLICATION ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN SOCIAL STUDIES AMONG STUDENTS OF COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20593783>

Abstract

The paper examined the influence of technological application on Social Studies teaching and learning among students of Colleges of Education in Ogun State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Population comprises all students of Colleges of Education in Ogun state, Nigeria. The sample size for this study comprises of 50 students in two (2) selected Colleges of Education in Ogun state to make a total of 100 respondents as sample. The colleges of education are the Federal college of education, Abeokuta and TaiSolarin College of Education, Ijebu-Ode. A self-developed questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. It was developed in closed-ended of agreed or disagreed. The instrument was moderated by experts who affirmed its validity. Reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha and the value of 0.73 was obtained which is reliable enough for this study. Data collected were analyzed using simple percentage, mean and standard deviation statistical tools. Findings revealed that both teachers and students generally hold positive attitudes toward the integration of technology in Social Studies education, with a significant majority acknowledging its potential to enhance engagement, understanding of complex concepts, and overall educational outcomes. The incorporation of digital tools and resources can transform traditional teaching methods, fostering a more interactive and student-centered learning environment. However, the successful implementation of technological tools requires adequate infrastructure, teacher training, and supportive policies. Findings also highlighted the challenges such as limited resources, digital literacy gaps, and infrastructural deficits continue to hinder its full potential in Nigerian colleges. It was therefore recommended that educational institutions should invest in the necessary technological infrastructure, including reliable internet access, modern computing devices, and multimedia resources. This will create an environment conducive to the effective use of technology in teaching and learning.

Keywords: Academic performance, College of education, Social Studies teaching, Social Studies learning, Technological application

Introduction

The rapid development of digital technology has significantly transformed various sectors, including education. In recent years, the integration of technology into teaching and learning processes has been widely recognized as a crucial factor in enhancing educational quality. Social Studies education according to Adediran (2022) has evolved as a multidisciplinary field that integrates concepts from various social science disciplines, including history, geography, economics, and political science. The aim of Social Studies is to prepare students to become informed and responsible citizens by equipping them with critical thinking, decision-making, and problem-solving skills (Mezieobi, 2019). In the Nigerian educational system, Social Studies plays a pivotal role in fostering national consciousness and promoting civic responsibilities, especially at the tertiary level (Ogundare, 2020). Historically, Social Studies education in Nigeria has undergone significant changes since its inception in the 1960s, with the objective of addressing the country's diverse socio-political challenges (Adeyemi & Ajiboye, 2017). However, teaching methods have largely remained traditional, which has led to calls for the integration of modern technological tools to enhance the learning experience.

Technological advancements have transformed many sectors, including education and the integration of technology into the educational system has created new learning environments that foster interactive and student-centered pedagogy (Adediran, 2022). According to Anderson and Dron (2021), educational technology encompasses a wide range of digital tools such as multimedia content, e-learning platforms, and mobile applications that support teaching and learning processes. These tools enable students to access information more readily, collaborate with peers, and develop higher-order thinking skills.

In the context of higher education, technology has become an essential component in enhancing the quality of teaching and learning. Scholars argue that technology improves students' engagement and helps cater to various learning styles (Clark & Mayer, 2016). For instance, multimedia presentations and virtual simulations can make abstract concepts more tangible and accessible to students, which is especially useful in subjects like Social Studies that involve complex social and political phenomena.

Several studies according to Adediran (2022) have examined the use of technology in Social Studies education both globally and within Nigeria. For instance, a study by Ayeni and Ojo (2022) revealed that the use of interactive whiteboards, educational software, and online resources significantly improved student engagement and understanding of Social Studies concepts in secondary schools in Lagos State. Similarly, Okafor (2021) found that digital simulations of historical events and government systems enhanced students' critical thinking skills and improved their ability to analyse social issues. In the Nigerian context, however, the level of technological integration in higher education remains low due to infrastructural challenges, limited access to digital tools, and inadequate training for teachers (Afolabi & Olayemi, 2020). Although the Nigerian government has initiated various policies aimed at promoting the use of technology in education, their implementation at the tertiary level, especially in Colleges of Education, has been inconsistent.

The relationship between technology use and academic performance has been widely explored in educational research. Studies according to Adediran, Atanda and Adelegun (2023) show that

the use of educational technologies can have a positive impact on students' academic performance when effectively implemented. According to Schmid et al. (2019), students who use digital tools such as e-learning platforms and virtual simulations tend to perform better in assessments compared to those relying solely on traditional methods. In Social Studies education, technological tools can help students grasp complex socio-political concepts, enhance their critical thinking, and promote collaboration (Donnelly & Boniface, 2017). For example, virtual tours of historical sites and online forums for discussing civic issues provide experiential learning opportunities that traditional teaching methods cannot offer. However, it is crucial to note that the effectiveness of these tools depends on how well they are integrated into the curriculum and whether teachers are adequately trained in their use (Sahin & Thompson, 2020).

Attitudes toward technology play a significant role in its adoption and effectiveness in the classroom. Research suggests that teachers' attitudes are often shaped by their comfort level with using technology and their perceptions of its value in education (Ertmer & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2019). In a study conducted by Akinyemi and Adedayo (2021), many Nigerian Social Studies teachers expressed positive attitudes toward using technology but cited a lack of proper training and resources as barriers to its effective use. Similarly, students' attitudes toward technology are influenced by their access to and familiarity with digital tools. Uzochukwu (2020) found that students in Colleges of Education in Ogun State showed a high level of enthusiasm for using technology in Social Studies, but they also pointed out challenges such as poor internet connectivity and lack of technical support. The study emphasized that both teachers and students require continuous support to maximize the benefits of technology in education.

Despite the benefits of technological application in Social Studies education, several challenges hinder its effective integration, especially in developing regions like Nigeria. Infrastructure is one of the most significant obstacles. Many schools and colleges lack reliable electricity, adequate internet access, and the necessary hardware to support digital learning (Fagbemi, 2021). Furthermore, a lack of digital literacy among teachers, coupled with insufficient professional development opportunities, further complicates the integration process (Kukul & Gökçearsan, 2022). Financial constraints also play a critical role. Colleges of Education in Ogun State often face budget limitations, making it difficult to invest in the necessary technology infrastructure (Oladele, 2022). In addition, there is a need for policy frameworks that support the long-term sustainability of technology integration in the education system.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this paper is to examine the influence of technological application on social studies teaching and learning of students in Colleges of Education in Ogun state. The specific objectives are to:

- i. analyze the impact of technology on students' academic performance in Social Studies in Colleges of Education in Ogun state.
- ii. evaluate the attitudes of teachers and students towards the use of technology in Social Studies education in Colleges of Education in Ogun state.

Research Questions

- i. How has the use of technology influenced students' academic performance in Social Studies in Colleges of Education in Ogun state?

- ii. What are the attitudes of teachers and students toward the integration of technology in Social Studies education in Colleges of Education in Ogun state?

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Population comprises all students of Colleges of Education in Ogun state, Nigeria. The sample size for this study comprises of 50 students in two (2) selected Colleges of Education in Ogun state to make a total of 100 respondents as sample. The colleges of education are the Federal college of education, Abeokuta and TaiSolarin College of Education, Ijebu-Ode. A self-developed questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. It was developed in closed-ended of agreed or disagreed. The instrument was moderated by experts who affirmed its validity. Reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha and the value of 0.73 was obtained which is reliable enough for this study. Data collected were analyzed simple percentage, mean and standard deviation statistical tools.

Presentation of Data Analysis and Results Discussion

Table 1: How has the use of technology influenced students' academic performance in Social Studies in Colleges of Education in Ogun State?

N/S	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Remarks
1	The use of technology in Social Studies classes has improved my understanding of key concepts.	47 (47%)	26 (26%)	18 (18%)	9 (9%)	3.11	Accepted
2	Digital tools (e.g., multimedia presentations, e-learning platforms) have made Social Studies lessons more engaging and easier to follow	51 (51%)	26 (26%)	17 (17%)	6 (6%)	3.22	Accepted
3	Technology has enhanced my ability to retain and recall Social Studies information for exams and assessments	18 (10.7%)	34 (33.3%)	36 (44%)	12 (12%)	2.58	Accepted
4	The integration of technology in Social Studies has positively impacted my overall academic performance in the subject.	17 (17%)	68 (68%)	13 (13%)	2 (2%)	3.00	Accepted
Weighted Mean = 2.98							

The data presented in Table 1 illustrates how the use of technology has influenced students' academic performance in Social Studies in Colleges of Education in Ogun State. Item 1 shows that a majority of students (47% strongly agree and 26% agree) believe that technology has improved their understanding of key concepts in Social Studies, with a mean score of 3.11, indicating a positive response. Similarly, Item 2 demonstrates that 51% of respondents strongly agree and 26% agree that digital tools, such as multimedia presentations and e-learning platforms, have made lessons more engaging and easier to follow. With a mean score of 3.22, this suggests a significant acceptance of technology's role in improving lesson delivery.

However, responses to Item 3 reflect more mixed opinions about technology's role in enhancing students' ability to retain and recall information, with only 10.7% strongly agreeing, 33.3% agreeing, and 44% disagreeing. The lower mean score of 2.58 suggests that while some students find technology beneficial, many do not believe it significantly improves retention for exams. Despite this, Item 4 reveals that 68% agree that the integration of technology has positively impacted their overall academic performance, with a mean score of 3.00, indicating a general consensus that technology plays a role in improving academic outcomes in Social Studies.

Table 2: What are the attitudes of teachers and students toward the integration of technology in Social Studies education in Colleges of Education in Ogun state?

	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Remarks
1	I believe that the use of technology improves the teaching and learning of Social Studies.	38 (38%)	36 (36%)	14 (14%)	12 (12%)	3.00	Accepted
2	Teachers in my institution are enthusiastic about incorporating technology into Social Studies lessons.	43 (43%)	29 (29%)	19 (19%)	9 (9%)	3.06	Accepted
3	Students find Social Studies more engaging when technology is used during lessons.	23 (23%)	37 (37%)	33 (33%)	7 (7%)	2.76	Accepted
4	The use of technology in Social Studies classes makes it easier to understand complex concepts	34 (34%)	45 (45%)	15 (15%)	6 (6%)	3.07	Accepted
	Weighted Mean = 2.97						

Table 2 presents data on the attitudes of teachers and students towards the integration of technology in Social Studies education in Colleges of Education in Ogun State. The first item, "I believe that the use of technology improves the teaching and learning of Social Studies," shows that 38% of respondents strongly agreed (SA) and 36% agreed (A), indicating that a majority (74%) perceive technology as beneficial for improving Social Studies education. This is supported by a mean score of 3.00, which signifies general acceptance of this statement. The second item, which explores teachers' enthusiasm for incorporating technology, shows that 43% strongly agreed, and 29% agreed, totalling 72% in favor. The mean score of 3.06 also indicates that the respondents believe teachers are positively inclined toward using technology in the classroom.

For the third item, "Students find Social Studies more engaging when technology is used during lessons," 23% strongly agreed and 37% agreed, with a combined agreement of 60%. While the acceptance level is lower than in previous items, the mean score of 2.76 still reflects an overall positive attitude towards technology making Social Studies more engaging. The fourth item, "The use of technology in Social Studies classes makes it easier to understand complex concepts," had the highest positive response, with 34% strongly agreeing and 45% agreeing, leading to a total of 79%. The mean score of 3.07 suggests that a strong majority view technology as an effective tool for simplifying difficult concepts. The weighted mean across all items is 2.97,

indicating a generally favourable attitude towards technology integration among teachers and students.

Discussion of findings

The results of research question 1 revealed how the use of technology has influenced students' academic performance in Social Studies in Colleges of Education in Ogun state. The finding is in line with Olayiwola and Adebayo (2021) who stated that the use of technology in Social Studies fosters student engagement and a deeper understanding of complex concepts, particularly through multimedia and interactive platforms. Furthermore, Ajayi (2022) suggests that while technology enhances engagement and comprehension, challenges related to information retention may persist if students do not actively interact with the content. Overall, these results align with the broader literature, which emphasizes the benefits of technology in enhancing academic performance but highlights the need for strategies that ensure better retention and recall of information.

Moreso, research question 2 shows the attitudes of teachers and students toward the integration of technology in Social Studies education in Colleges of Education in Ogun state. These findings are consistent with previous studies of Ajayi (2022) who highlighted that the integration of multimedia tools in Social Studies improves students' comprehension and critical thinking skills. Similarly, Adebayo and Olayiwola (2021) found that educators who are enthusiastic about adopting technology in their teaching experience enhanced classroom engagement and student participation. These studies align with the results in Table 2, which show that both teachers and students hold favorable views on the role of technology in improving teaching and learning outcomes in Social Studies.

Conclusion

Based on the study, both teachers and students generally hold positive attitudes toward the integration of technology in Social Studies education, with a significant majority acknowledging its potential to enhance engagement, understanding of complex concepts, and overall educational outcomes. The incorporation of digital tools and resources can transform traditional teaching methods, fostering a more interactive and student-centered learning environment. However, the successful implementation of technological tools requires adequate infrastructure, teacher training, and supportive policies. While empirical studies highlight the benefits of technology in education, challenges such as limited resources, digital literacy gaps, and infrastructural deficits continue to hinder its full potential in Nigerian colleges.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that;

- i. Educational institutions should invest in the necessary technological infrastructure, including reliable internet access, modern computing devices, and multimedia resources. This will create an environment conducive to the effective use of technology in teaching and learning.
- ii. Regular training and professional development programs should be implemented to equip teachers with the skills and knowledge required to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. Workshops, seminars, and online courses can enhance educators' confidence and proficiency in utilizing digital tools.

- iii. The Social Studies curriculum should be reviewed and revised to incorporate technological applications explicitly. This can include the use of e-learning platforms, digital simulations, and multimedia content that align with learning objectives and enhance students' understanding of complex societal issues.
- iv. Encourage collaborative learning experiences that utilize technology, such as online discussions, virtual group projects, and interactive simulations. These approaches can foster engagement and critical thinking among students, promoting deeper learning in Social Studies.
- v. Establish mechanisms for the continuous monitoring and evaluation of technology integration in Social Studies education. Feedback from both teachers and students can help identify areas for improvement and inform future strategies for effective technology use.
- vi. Colleges of Education should seek partnerships with technology companies and educational organizations to gain access to the latest tools, resources, and training opportunities. Collaborating with external partners can provide additional support and expertise in technology integration.

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